

DigiVet - Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

WP2 - Deliverable 2.3: Publicly available and reproducible holistic data analysis workflows for the case studies.

Authors

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This document signposts the software-based deliverables for each of the three case studies. We note that each of the deliverables is provided in the form of either code/scripts or full packages in the statistical programming language R; we chose this software due to it being open source, free of charge, active development over a 25+ year period, and strong uptake within the wider community of veterinary epidemiology and applied statistics (including within the project team). R can be obtained free of charge via the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN): <https://cran.r-project.org>

We also note that active development of many of the tools shown here is expected to continue beyond the life span of the project; we therefore give installation instructions for both the static versions of the tools (created at the end of the project with fixed DOI) as well as the versions of the tools where development is expected to continue.

Case study 1

The primary output for CS1 is the goldeneye encryption workflow for safe sharing and storage of sensitive data, which we used initially for *Salmonella* Dublin test data but have since made sufficiently generic that it can be used with any dataset, either existing objects within R or external data files in any file format (including Excel, any binary data format, and any text-based data format). This workflow also provides encryption utilities to reduce the storage capacity requirements for data archival.

The goldeneye package can be installed in one of two ways; either via the repositories on GitHub (either the static DigiVet project repository or the development repository), or via the drat repository maintained by the Danish project partner. Instructions are given below.

Via drat (recommended)

Simply type the following to install the latest release version of goldeneye:

```
install.packages("goldeneye",
  repos=c("https://cran.rstudio.com/", "https://ku-awdc.github.io/drat/"))
```

Via GitHub

You will first need to install the remotes package in the usual way:

```
install.packages("remotes")
```

Then type the one of the following commands to either install goldeneye version 0.9.6-6 from the DigiVet project's static repository, or the current version of goldeneye from the active development repository:

```
remotes::install_github("digivet-consortium/goldeneye",
  build_vignettes=TRUE)
remotes::install_github("ku-awdc/goldeneye", build_vignettes=TRUE)
```

The static repository is also stored on Zenodo with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10381612 (this is documented at <https://github.com/digivet-consortium/goldeneye>).

Getting started

Full instructions for new users can be obtained via the vignette within R:

```
vignette("goldeneye")
```

This vignette, as well as the full package documentation, are also provided as an appendix to this deliverable – full technical details of the encryption workflow are provided in this vignette document and are therefore not repeated here.

Case study 2

DOI for AMView (which includes data analysis scripts under the data_processing directory) is 10.5281/zenodo.10400887

Case study 2 – Antimicrobial use

CS2 - BACKGROUND

Recent legislation in EU (article 57 of regulation 2019/6, EU Commission, 2019, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/6/2022-01-28>) implies that the member states will be required to report antimicrobial sales and use (ASU) to EU from 2024. It has been possible for European countries to report antimicrobial sales data on a voluntary basis to the European Medicines Agency (EMA, <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/veterinary->

[regulatory/overview/antimicrobial-resistance/european-surveillance-veterinary-antimicrobial-consumption-esvac#interactive-esvac-database-section](#)) since 2009.

In WP2, the deliverable 2.2 suggest and document a common data structure for antimicrobial use (AMU) data (Table 1). The common data structure in this case study is inspired by the requirements for reporting AMU to EU, but is adapted to also include other information that can be useful for further analysis. AMU data in the common data structure format can be used as input for the dashboard developed in WP2.4. As a result of the workshop "DigiVet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health" on 26th October 2023, the data structure was slightly updated. The R scripts for transforming the data has not been updated to reflect these changes.

The processes or workflows to format source data into the common data structure will differ between the countries and may also require different data sources combined. Nevertheless, the conceptual workflow may be more similar between countries. Thus, in this deliverable, we present an example workflow using the Norwegian data to show how one can transform their raw data into the common data structure, which can then be visualized by the dashboard developed in the project (D2.4).

The requirement to use the common data structure and the tools developed in WP2 may vary a lot for different countries (depending on already existing workflows and tools), but we hope that the results of this report and other deliverables in DigiVet can be of use to other countries outside of DigiVet to enhance digitalisation of AMU-data.

Table 1 - Overview of the suggested common data structure in case study 2 on antimicrobial use (see deliverable 2.2).

category	variable	explanation
Entry	EntryID	Unique identifier of the entry
	TypeOfDataSource	Type of entry in database, for example if it is a pharmacy sale or journal record
	IncludeAsUse	States if the entry should be included in calculations of AMU
Date	DateTransaction	Date of sale transaction (if the entry is a sale)
	DateTreatment	Date of treatment
	DateOther	Other available date
	DateOtherComment	Comment to explain DateOther
Geographical information	Country	2-letter country code (ISO 3166-1 alpha-2)
	NUTS2	Level 2 of nomenclature of territorial units for statistics classification, from European Union
	NUTS3	Level 3 of nomenclature of territorial units for statistics classification, from European Union
	GeoComment	Comment to explain what geographic location is specified (e.g. location of the pharmacy or treated herd)
Animal information	HerdID	Identification of herd, if applicable.
	AnimalType	Animal species (combined with production type in some cases)
	ProductionType	Type of production
	Gender	Gender of the treated animal/s
	AgeCategory	Age category of treated animal/s
Treatment and medication information	TreatmentPurpose	Purpose of the treatment.
	Indication	Indication, symptom or medical condition that was the reason for treatment.
	Diagnosis	Diagnosis, free text at the moment
	AdministrationMethod	Administration method of medical product
	TreatedUnit	Information on whether the entry reports treatment to an individual or group of animals
	NumberOfAnimals	Number of treated animals
	MedicalProductName	Name of the medical product
	MedicalProductCode	Code identifying medical product
	ATCcode	The ATC (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical) code of the medical product
ActiveIngredient	Name of active ingredient	
	ActiveIngredientMg	Amount of active ingredient, given in mg

CS2 - CONCEPTUAL WORK FLOW

The following principle steps were identified for calculating AMU.

1. Access usage and/or sales data.
2. Combine the usage and sales data with the information on active substances and concentrations.
3. Filter for antibacterial substances by ATC-codes.
4. Transform the data to the common data structure and calculate AMU.

CS2 - APPLIED WORKFLOW (NORWEGIAN EXAMPLE)

Access usage and/or sales data

In Norway, there is one data source for AMU, i.e. the veterinary prescriptions and usage register (VetReg), which is owned and hosted by the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (NFSA). The register includes all usage of medicines by veterinarians in production animals, all prescriptions to animal owners delivered from pharmacies, and all deliveries from pharmacies to veterinarians. The AMU is calculated from veterinary usage and prescriptions to animal owners.

In addition the sales from wholesalers to detailers (pharmacies) are collected by the National Public Health Institute (NPHI). The sales data is used to check the coverage of the data in VetReg.

The Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI) performs the calculation of ASU in animals for the national and international reporting on behalf of the competent authorities in Norway.

The VetReg data is exported in csv format from NFSA's database and imported into a database at NVI.

Combine the usage and sales data with the information on active substances and concentrations

In VetReg the item number of the medicinal products is given. The information on package size, active substances, ATC-code and concentration is given in the service "Forskrivnings- og ekspedisjonsstøtte" (FEST) hosted and owned by Norwegian Medicine Agency (NoMA). The register FEST covers medicines currently in use. Therefore, NVI has established internal support registers with historical registrations from FEST as well as registers for item numbers that are reported in VetReg but were not included in FEST for various reasons.

The VetReg data is combined with the medicine list generated from FEST and internal support registers by item number.

Filter for antibacterial substances by ATC-codes

A list of ATC-codes for which ASU should be reported to EMA is given in the Commission delegated regulation 2021/578 in the Annex ([EUR-Lex - 32021R0578 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#)).

The VetReg data is filtered so that only records with relevant ATC-codes are included in the AMU data.

Transform the data to the common data structure and calculate AMU

For each registration in the AMU data the transformation includes:

- Calculation of AMU
- Identification of region

- Identification of production type
- Standardisation of column names and column values

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the Norwegian workflow to calculate AMU based on VetReg (the Norwegian database for veterinary prescriptions and veterinary use of medicines) and the register with information on medical products (FEST).

CS2 - DETAILED WORKFLOW (NORWEGIAN EXAMPLE)

The detailed workflow exemplified with Norwegian data is given in the annex "Deliverable 2.3, Case study 2 - AMU. Detailed Workflow (Norwegian example)" and the corresponding R scripts is found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400887>.

Prepare AMU raw data

Figure 1 – Sketch of process in Norway to combine data sources into raw data on antimicrobial use (AMU). VetReg is the Norwegian Food Safety Authority's database for veterinary prescriptions and veterinary use of medicines and NoMA (Norwegian Medicine Agency) medicine register contains information on medical products.

Calculate AMU

Figure 2 - Overview of process in Norway to calculate the AMU based on raw data.

Case study 3

Commercial pig movements are an important factor in the spread of African swine fever (ASF). The analysis of these movements can provide valuable intelligence for preparedness and outbreak response. For example, network analysis can determine a movement network's effectiveness at transmitting infection, and the relative importance of different holdings and connections therein. Additionally, incorporating detailed movement data into disease transmission models can improve the accuracy of predictions of these models, such as final outbreak size, and the speed at which this is reached. The effective use of pig movement data for these purposes is, however, complicated by a variety of challenges, including issues relating to data, and requirements for specific analytic expertise.

The aim of WP2 for CS3 is to address these challenges by developing a toolkit that facilitates the dataflow from pig movement data to network analysis and to transmission models of ASF, and that helps users with interpreting the outputs from these analyses. This toolkit comes in the form of an open-source R package, *movenet* (<https://digiVet-consortium.github.io/movenet/>), and an accompanying interactive app to cater to users who prefer a graphical user interface. These tools are being developed through all tasks in WP2.

In Task 2.2, we focused on addressing data-related issues: we developed a flexible data parsing functionality that converts datasets to a common data structure, and a privacy-enhancing workflow.

For this deliverable, we developed workflows for the integration of movement and holding data into disease transmission models, and for network analysis. The transmission modelling workflow links up with the modelling package SimInf ("A framework for data-driven stochastic disease spread simulations", <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/SimInf/index.html>), by converting movement data and/or holding coordinates into a transmission matrix that can serve as input to a custom pre-compiled holding-unit SEIR model of ASF (SEIRcm). The network analysis workflow links up with the Statnet suite of packages (<https://statnet.org/packages/>) to generate dynamic network representations of movement data and to determine a range of network metrics relevant to disease spread. This workflow produces a standardised, downloadable report, with tables and figures displaying basic network properties such as the number of active holdings and edges (overall and over time), static network analyses of periodic

(monthly or yearly) snapshots, temporal analyses including ingoing and outgoing contact chains (reachability), and component analysis. Interpretive text is also provided, to support decision-making and to facilitate uptake by users with limited network analysis expertise.

The ensemble of *movenet* workflows developed for CS3 is visualised in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Conceptual diagram of the workflows developed for CS3 in WP2. The *movenetapp* graphical user interface (developed in Task 2.4) is also shown.

The *movenet* package is open-source software, and will continue to be developed; the version released with this Deliverable can be downloaded from Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10412758>) and any latest version from GitHub (<https://github.com/digivet-consortium/movenet>). The software includes function and workflow documentation, and a README file with installation instructions; these can also be accessed through the package's web page (<https://digivet-consortium.github.io/movenet/>).

The associated *siminf4movenet* package with the SEIRcm transmission model is also available from Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10286650>) and GitHub (<https://github.com/digivet-consortium/siminf4movenet>).